

Ambedkar’s Idea of Equality: A Universal Necessity Beyond Borders and Generations Pavitra

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ABSTRACT:

This Article tries to throw some bright light on Dr.B.R.Ambedkar’s thoughts or views on “Equality” from different angles. The thoughts of Ambedkar’s on the concept called, “Equality” is beyond the borders like; Time, Region, Areas, Nations, Concepts, Generations, Centuries etc. This border free or limit free or time free ideas of Ambedkar on “Equality” speaks about the relevance of his Ideas or Thoughts for all time and can be considered as universal necessity.

“Equality” is nothing but going according to the Nature without making any discrimination on the grounds of Caste, Creed, Gender, Socio-politico–Economic status, Cultural practices, Traditions, Norms, Ideas, Practices etc. It is a principle of treating all fairly. “Equality” is just like treating all equally in front of the Nature. “Equality” is like inclusion of all fit and eligible people with equal opportunities in all activities of the Public, Society or the System. The concept called “Equality” speaks about Human Dignity, Social Justice and Legal Rights etc.

The idea of “Equality” is depended upon the concept called, “Inclusivity” as per Ambedkar’s views with different dimensions like;

Social Equality, Political Equality, Economic Equality, Legal Equality, Gender Equality, Educational Equality, Global Equality, Cultural Equality, Constitutional Equality etc and these different dimensions of Equality must be co-existed with the values called Justice, Laws, Ethics and Rights etc.

This Article also speaks about how Ambedkar’s views on “Equality” is co-connected with Annihilation of Caste Discrimination, Women Empowerment, Eradication of Gender discrimination etc. Relevance of his thoughts in contemporary India and also beyond Centuries or Generations or Nations etc.

KEYWORDS:

Equality, Ambedkar, Inclusiveness, Social, Political, Economic, Constitutional, Gender, Generation, Discrimination, Inequality.

INTRODUCTION:

Dr.B.R.Ambedkar, also known as Babasaheb is remembered for all time because of his great efforts and contributions towards Drafting Indian Constitution in a just, inclusive and balanced way. He had restlessly struggled for removal of Social, Cultural, and Religious evils of the Nation and tried to provide Justice, Freedom, Equality etc for all Citizens of India. Though he had a very bad experience during his life time from Upper Classes of the Society, he used to think for the well being of all through a great means called, Constitution of India. His thoughts were beyond the Caste, Community, Gender, Religion, Region, etc. In total his views on Equality were free from discriminations and beyond borders.

Dr. B.R.Ambedkar has discussed about the concept “Equality” in his so called Works, Speeches, News Papers ; The Annihilation of Caste, The Buddha and his Dhamma, His Final Speech to the Constituent Assembly, Mook Nayak and Bahishkrit Bharat etc.

The views or thoughts of Ambedkar on Equality has inspired the globally recognized Foreign Universities like; Columbia University–USA, London School of Economics–UK, Heidelberg University–Germany etc to include Ambedkar’s thoughts, his Biography, Principles, Ideas, Writings, Articles etc in their curriculum and Research Projects on the topics like; Women Empowerment, Gender Discrimination, Inclusive India, Movements against Inequality, Social Justice, Political Participation etc.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objective of the study is to make the readers understand properly regarding Ambedkar’s thoughts on “Equality” as Universal, beyond the borders, beyond time, beyond generation etc. They are like, motivational paths for other Countries who are fighting against Caste based, Color based, Creed based, Gender based and Status based discrimination and an inspiration for Labor movements, Industrial Workers Movements, Human Rights Movements etc throughout the Universe.

Secondary Sources have been used to understand how Ambedkar’s thoughts on “Equality” are Universal, Relevant, all time contemporary and beyond the borders and limits etc.

AMBEDKAR’S VIEWS ON EQUALITY:

Ambedkar’s thoughts on “Equality” is a combination (according to the time and circumstances) of different Theories of Equality such as, “Feminist Equality” means, addressing gender–based systemic inequalities and providing equal opportunities to women section of the society for

equal work or equal service;

“Rawlsian Justice as Fairness” means, inequalities are acceptable if they benefit the least advantaged. In this sense, Ambedkar thinks about Reservation System for assisting those populations with least advantaged and with this reason they are given fixed percentage of representation, reservation or participation in the different systems or areas or fields for their all round development and active involvement under “Protective Discrimination” concept.

Marxist Equality means, equal outcomes and redistribution of wealth and this ideology of Marx is followed by Ambedkar in fighting for Labor Rights, Social Justice, Gender Equality, Industrial Policies, Special provisions for working women group at Industrial areas etc.

As the views or thoughts of Ambedkar on Equality is free from limitations like; fixed borders, time specific, region specific, generation specific, gender specific, caste and communities specific, religion specific, culture specific, traditions specific etc, they are relevant for contemporary India as well as for other same kind of countries and also for Universal issues. His thoughts on Equality can be taken as motivational ideology for movements against issues like; Gender Inequality, Social Injustice, Partiality in Political Participation, Race Discrimination, Economic Status Discrimination, Labor Community Issues, Caste Discrimination, Social Evils, Educational Issues and Cultural Clashes etc in India.

His views on Gender and Labor Class Rights are globally inspiring the contemporary world to fight against discrimination on the basis of Gender and to fight for their equal Rights and strongly motivating the Labor class to ask for their Rights, minimum facilities and securities etc. In this sense, his thoughts on “Equality” is 100 percent beyond borders as they just not speak only about Dalit and Co-communities, but also for all citizens of India. His views were free from all kind of borders and limits. They are Universal, all time relevant, beyond Centuries, Generations etc.

DR.B.R.AMBEDKAR AND CONSTITUTION OF INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO EQUALITY:

Dr.B.R.Ambedkar, an architect of Indian Constitution as well as an eminent Social Reformer has championed the idea of “Equality” in all dimensions like; Social Equality, Political Equality, Economic Equality, Legal Equality, Gender Equality, Educational Equality etc.

Equality in the Indian Constitution is a Fundamental Right

guaranteed by Articles 14 to 18, ensuring equal status and opportunity for all citizens through the Rule of Law. Ambedkar has used the Constitution as a platform to bring Social Justice, Equality, Inclusive Society, Eradication of Caste System, Political Democracy, Fundamental Education for all, Just India, Women Empowerment, Active Representation and Social Democracy etc.

Many newly introduced Policies, Rules, Regulations and Welfare Schemes of the Center and State Governments are working accordingly with Ambedkar's opinions on Equality.

The Central Government Schemes like;

1. Stand Up India- For Economic or Financial Inclusivity of skilled sections of the society.
2. Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana- For Housing Facilities for marginalized communities.
3. Beti Bachao-Beti Padhao- For providing basic education to all Girls and to combat Child Marriage Practices etc.

The Karnataka State Government Schemes like;

1. Guarantee Schemes like Gruha Jyoti, Gruha Laxmi, Anna Bhagya, Yuva Nidhi, Shakti etc to bring Women Section of the Society to main streams, to make them financially independent, to increase their mobility for different reasons, to provide basic food facilities to the needy and to motivate the Youth Students to prepare for their future.
2. A recent introduction of the new policy called "Paid Menstrual Leave" for working women (18-52 years of age) with 12 days paid leaves in a year.

The other State Government Schemes;

1. DR.Bhimarao Ambedkar Arhik Kalyan Yojana (Madhya Pradesh)
2. Ambedkar Antyodaya Yojana (Uttar Pradesh)

RELEVANCE OF AMBEDKAR'S THOUGHTS IN GLOBAL CONTEXT:

The views of Ambedkar on Equality is not just applicable to Indian Society alone, but also can be referred at Global level. Because, issues related with inequality, injustice, discrimination etc are Universal in nature. These issues are having inbuilt solutions throughout the Ambedkar's thoughts on Equality, Social Justice, Caste and Class free Society, Women Empowerment, Human Rights, Abolition of Evil Practices of Indian Society etc.

CONCLUSION:

“Equality beyond borders–Dr.B.R.Ambedkar’s thoughts” is an all time and universal concept. His views on Equality are just like a “Vaccine” for many past, contemporary and future issues of Indian Society as well as beyond the borders of Indian Nation. His thoughts are beyond Communities, Classes, Gender, Centuries, Generations, Physical and Principles based borders. The views of Ambedkar on Equality act as a boosting vaccine for all these issues accordingly.

Many Governments are taking the “Vision” of Ambedkar’s thoughts on Equality as their “Mission” for welfare of the Citizens of India. This vision includes all community based people of the Nation as a whole. It is for all without any borders. His vision is also relevant for finding solutions to upcoming issues of the Nation. They are eternal until a just and equal society exists.

His views on Equality should not be limited to Constitution of India, but also should be practiced in our day to day life for bringing “a Welfare State or an Ideal State”. Learning has no borders. So, preaching also has no borders.

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